

Elongation potential of different plant parts in some advanced deepwater rice lines. Ghagharaghat, Bahraich, India. Values over the columns are increase in percentage.

Increase in plant height, leaf sheath, and leaf blade in some advanced IRRI deepwater lines and checks.

Variety or line	Elongation (mm/d)			Survival score ^a
	Plant height	Leaf blade	Leaf sheath	
IR31142-14-1-1-3-1-1-2	24	14	4	9
IR33284-4-502-1-3-2-2	52	21	20	5
IR33284-4-503-1-1-2-3-3	20	10	18	7
IR39509-46-3-2-2	23	21	19	9
IR39657-B-B-B-1	23	32	4	9
IR48279-42-2	23	16	16	9
IR48279-71-3	63	5	10	9
IR48279-73-2	25	22	7	9
IR48279-75-2	37	25	15	7
IR48310-5-3	63	44	10	3
IR5135-3-4	50	32	5	7
IR54300-50	62	44	19	5
Jalmagna	43	27	20	5
IR36	34	3	7	9

^a Standard evaluation system for rice.

502-1-3-2-2. Internode elongation was not pronounced except in Jalmagna, IR33284-4-502-1-3-2-2, and IR33284-503-1-1-2-3-3.

IR48310-5-3 and IR54300-50 had the highest plant elongation potential, with survival scores of 3 and 5, respectively. □

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific understanding.

Stress tolerance – adverse temperature

Effect of low temperature on winter rice in Andhra Pradesh

N. Kulkarni and H. S. Nagaraj Rao, Agricultural Research Institute, Andhra Pradesh (AP) Agricultural University, Hyderabad 500030, India

Sudden rice leaf yellowing and turning to orange were noticed in popular cultivars Tella Hamsa, Satya, Rasi, IR36, and WGL 48684 the last week of Feb 1989 in Telangana region, AP. Extensive surveys established that this had occurred within 2 d.

We examined the temperature data. On 19 and 20 Feb, the maximum temperature at Hyderabad was 34.4 °C. On 19 Feb, the minimum temperature was 16 °C. But on 20 Feb, minimum temperature was 7 °C. The sudden drop in temperature lasted 2 d. The rice cultivars were in different growth phases and were affected differently.

- IR36 had severe cold injury.
- Tella Hamsa and Rasi were in the vegetative phase, and had little cold injury.
- Tella Hamsa, in panicle initiation and boot leaf stages, had normal leaves. But 2 wk later, panicles were found to be chaffy. Pollen grains examined under the microscope were sterile.
- Low temperatures of 7-12 °C lasted 10 d. Severity of cold injury was proportionate to the variation in temperature.
- Plants in the shade exhibited the least cold injury symptoms.
- All cultivars affected by cold in the vegetative phase recovered when temperatures rose to more than 16 °C. The recovery of WGL 48684 was fast. Cold injury due to low temperatures observed in thousands of hectares necessitates a program for breeding cold-tolerant cultivars for the Telangana region. □